

The Pastor: A Man of Frailty and Virtues

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“A good shepherd, a shepherd according to the heart of God, is the greatest treasure that the good God can give to a parish, and one of the most precious gifts of the divine mercy.”

Introduction

Pope Francis addressed his brother priests on St. John Vianney’s 160th death anniversary. He found in St. Vianney a model for priests of today. The church considers his heart to be a symbol of love, commitment and a sign of great holiness. Saint John Vianney, the French parish priest, is venerated in the Catholic Church as a saint and as the patron saint of parish priests. He is often referred to as the “Curé d’Ars” or the parish priest of Ars. He is internationally known for his priestly and pastoral work in his parish in Ars, France. He was able to transform his community and surroundings radically. This was possible, as many Catholics believe, because of his saintly life, mortification, persevering ministry in the sacrament of confession, and ardent devotion to the Eucharist and the Blessed Virgin Mary.

J M Vianney: A Model for Pastors

Pope Francis wrote the pastoral letter on the Feast of Vianney in order to support and encourage the priests so that they do great work in the midst of trials and temptations. He is aware of the fact that the world we are living in is a world full of difficulties and at the same time having many opportunities for tremendous work in the vineyard of the Lord. To carry on with this task one needs tremendous courage and constant encouragement, appreciation and commitment. Saint John Mary Vianney taught his parishioners primarily by the witness of his life. It was from his example that they learned to pray, halting frequently before the tabernacle for a visit to Jesus in the Blessed Sacrament. The dedication and holiness with which Vianney humbly served the tiny village of Ars, France not only transformed the lives of its 230 residents, but also began to affect the lives of Catholics throughout France and across Europe. Thousands of people began traveling to Ars to hear Vianney's powerful homilies and many people wanted him to hear their confessions. It was usual for him to spend up to sixteen hours a day in the confessional. He strongly believed that at the foundation of his pastoral commitment, the priest must have an intimate personal union with Christ, which he must cultivate and allow growing day by day. It is only if he is in love with Christ that the priest can teach others about this union, this intimate friendship with the Divine Master. He can touch the heart of people and open them up to the merciful love of the Lord. St. John Vianney exemplifies a life of sacrificial love, holy boldness and courageous perseverance. His example is relevant to our time.

There is no doubt that St. John Vianney was an extraordinary priest; but can he be a realistic model for the priests of today, many of whom have multiple parishes and diocesan responsibilities? The saints are always there to be a source of encouragement; to show us that someone just as human as us, struggling with many of the same temptations and vices we struggle with, has, through their openness to God's grace, attained eternal happiness in the beatific vision. Today's priests, then, should not look to St. John Vianney and think that they could never be like him; rather, they are invited to look to his pastoral zeal and prayerful dedication as a way to approach the pastoral situation particular to their own parish and diocese. We do not have to be like him; his time, people and place are different; moreover, each context is different, and person is unique. The laity are also invited and encouraged to pray to St. John Vianney, that he may intercede for their priests. As lay pastoral ministers become more of an integral part of every parish team, the life and holiness of St. John Vianney should encourage all to work tirelessly for the Gospel so that all may have a chance to dwell in the love of the heart of Christ.

Four Virtues by Pope Francis

Pope Francis makes use of four different perspectives to address the priests. It is insightful to deal with each of these.

1. Pain

The pope is aware of the fact that there are some priests who leave everything behind to engage themselves in the daily life of the people of the parish. These priests are ready to endure the difficulties with patience, commitment and courage. There are some good priests who suffer for the

mistakes of other priests. Even Church superiors and other priests misunderstand them. In spite of such difficulties, there are priests who generously persevere in their mission. Pope Francis understands them as brother priests, who have quietly “left all behind” in order to immerse themselves in the daily life of their communities. Like the Curé of Ars, they serve “in the trenches”, bearing the burden of the day and the heat, confronting an endless variety of situations in their effort to care for and accompany God’s people. Many of the priests, often without fanfare and at personal cost, amid weariness, infirmity and sorrow, carry out their mission of service to God and to the people. In some places, some priests feel themselves attacked and blamed for crimes they did not commit. The pope feels one with them in such situations. “Instead, I have called you friends” (John 15: 15).

If in the past, omission may itself have been a kind of response, today we desire conversion, transparency, sincerity and solidarity with victims to become our concrete way of moving forward. Pope Francis acknowledges and appreciates the courageous and steadfast example; in the times of turbulence, shame and pain, they demonstrate that they have joyfully put their lives on the line for the sake of the Gospel. I am convinced that, to the extent that we remain faithful to God’s will, these present times of ecclesial purification will make us more joyful and humble, and prove, in the not distant future, very fruitful. “Let us not grow discouraged! The Lord is purifying his Bride and converting all of us to himself. He is rescuing us from hypocrisy, from the spirituality of appearances. He is breathing forth his Spirit in order to restore the beauty of his Bride, caught in adultery”. If we go through the history of the church, we know that similar

things have happened before; and each of us can say it is our history too. In the end, through the sense of shame, we will continue to act as shepherds. Our humble repentance, expressed in silent tears before these atrocious sins and the unfathomable grandeur of God's forgiveness, is the beginning of a renewal of our holiness.

2. Gratitude

Our vocation to priesthood, more than our own choice, is a response to the Lord's unmerited call. We do well to return constantly to those passages of the Gospel where we see Jesus praying, choosing and calling others to be with him, and to be sent out to proclaim the message (Mk 3:14). If we can trust the words of Jesus then from that flame, we can light a fire for today and every day, and bring heat and light to our brothers and sisters. "That flame ignites a humble joy, a joy which sorrow and distress cannot dismay, a good and gentle joy." One of the bad temptations that we can have is to keep brooding over our troubles, for then we lose our perspective, our good judgement and our courage. It is often said that gratitude is the best attitude and can become a powerful way of dealing with life. Only if we are able to contemplate and feel genuine gratitude for all those ways we have experienced God's love, generosity, solidarity and trust, as well as his forgiveness, patience, forbearance and compassion, will we allow the Spirit to grant us the freshness that can renew our life and mission. Once it is done then we can hear the Lord repeat his summons: "Do not be afraid; from now on you will be fishers of men" (Lk 5:10). "For his mercy endures forever." We need to understand that the Lord triumphs through weakness (cf. 2 Cor 12:9). He continues to sustain us and to renew his call and thus we are

“capable of warming people’s hearts, walking at their side in the dark, talking with them and even entering into their night and their darkness, without losing our way”. Something we need to be happy that there were times when, with great emotion, we have embraced sinners, healed wounds, warmed hearts and showed the tenderness and compassion of the Good Samaritan (cf. Lk 10:25 ff). If we can reach out to people who are in need, in other words our accessibility, closeness, readiness to draw near to the flesh of our suffering brothers and sisters then we become good Samaritans. This in turn will lead to adopting a simple and austere way of life, rejecting privileges that have nothing to do with the Gospel. He blesses us with the gift of contemplating that faithful People “in those parents who raise their children with immense love, in those men and women who work hard to support their families, in the sick, in elderly religious who never lose their smile. In their daily perseverance, I see the holiness of the Church militant”.

3. Encouragement

When we feel confused or in difficulty or when we are faced with an unprecedented challenge, it is often helpful to read a few words of encouragement to not only encourage ourselves, but to inspire us to be an encouraging force for others. Faced with painful experiences, all of us need to be comforted and encouraged. One good way of testing our hearts as pastors is to ask how we confront suffering. We can often act like the Levite or the priest in the parable, stepping aside and ignoring the injured man (cf. Lk 10:31-32). We have the case of Prophet Jonah in the OT and we are constantly tempted to flee to a safe haven. In different ways, we experience them in our day-to-day life, namely,

individualism, spiritualism, living in a little world. All of us are aware of a sadness that can turn into a habit and lead us slowly to accept evil and injustice by quietly telling us: “It has always been like this”. Gradually in the midst of pain, we have been transformed and transfigured by the Lord and, like Job, we can exclaim: “I knew you then only by hearsay, but now I have seen you with my own eyes” (Job 42:2). If we do not have this foundational experience, all the hard work that we do will only lead to frustration and disappointment. In this prayer, we know that we are never alone. The genuine prayer of a pastor embraces both the Spirit who cries out “Abba, Father!” (cf. Gal 4:6), and the people who have been entrusted to his care.

4. Praise

The fourth perspective that Pope Francis speaks of is, Praise. He begins with the acclamation of Mary’s magnificat, “My soul proclaims the greatness of the Lord” (Lk 1:46). To contemplate Mary is to believe once again in the revolutionary nature of love and tenderness. In her, we see that humility and tenderness are not virtues of the weak but of the strong, who need not treat others poorly in order to feel important themselves. We need to affirm that God takes away even the hardest obstacles against which our hopes and expectations crash: death, sin, fear, worldliness. Human history does not end before a tombstone, because today it encounters the “living stone”.

Conclusion

Fr. Pedro Arrupe, S.J. (late Superior General of the SJ) once said, nothing is more practical than finding God, i.e., than falling in love in a quite absolute, final way. What you

are in love with, what seizes your imagination will affect everything. It will decide what will get you out of bed in the morning, what you will do with your evenings, how you spend your weekends, what you read, whom you know, what breaks your heart, and what amazes you with joy and gratitude. Fall in love, stay in love, and it will decide everything.

Many of us are aware of the challenge that priests face as they strive toward the goal of living like Christ. They acknowledge their individual powerlessness but say yes to God's power working in them. They become burden-bearers for Christ and His people. In presenting themselves for the sacrament of Holy Orders, they step out in faith and into something much greater than themselves. Their good example helps the people of God to do the same. Jesus made it clear that an identifying factor of a true shepherd is that they defend the flock against wolves (John 10:12-13).moral truths found among non-Christians, also their social life and culture.”